

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING OF THE SECOND LANGUAGE AND ITS DIFFICULTIES

Qulaxmedova Gulnora Abduraximovna

Tashkent the Institute of Finance

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Annotation: There have been so many offers in English language teaching in the education technology market in recent years , the question is, “What method do you teach?” The question becomes more relevant, as evidenced by the growing level of consumers of intellectual products. In our fast-paced world, where the education market offers all kinds of language courses , those who see time as gold and want to develop their work, this article helps them. So how effective are these teaching methods ? Do they give the expected n result?

Key words: communication, education, witness, science, preparation, standards.

All people living on earth are not only witnesses to the rapid change of the multifaceted world , but also direct participants in complex and continuous processes such as the development and advancement of world culture, science and technology. It is important to study English , which is one of the world's leading languages and has become the second language of communication for 40 percent of the world's population today . In a short period of time , state standards for the system of continuing education in foreign languages in our country have been developed, the requirements for the level of preparation of graduates of all stages of education have been set. Continuing education system of standards of knowledge of the universal language of the European Council on Foreign Pan: learning, teaching, assessment '(CEFR) was developed based on the requirements. A team of experts led by Rod Bolbayto and Davis Alan from the UK was involved to ensure that the state education standards were thorough in all respects .

Given that there have been so many offers in English language teaching in the education technology market in recent years , the question is, “What method do you teach?” The question becomes more relevant, as evidenced by the growing level of consumers of intellectual products. In our fast-paced world, where the education market offers all kinds of language courses , those who see time as gold and want to develop their work, study and business are often referred to as “Learn English in Two Weeks ”, “Effective Express Method”, “Ongosti English”. language"and other similar courses. So how effective are these teaching methods ? Do they give the expected n result?

In the recent past, the teaching of English has focused mainly on grammar . It took a lot of time to read and translate texts, and sometimes to memorize “topics” and write dictation to revive even a little bit of uniformity , and this process required a lot of hard work . Today, the main supply in the language market is formed depending on consumer demand . According to SG Ter-Minasova, a leading specialist in linguistics and methods of teaching foreign languages , “Today, the study of foreign languages, especially English, has become more relevant due to the functionalization of language teaching and the intensification of integration processes . But modern language learners are not interested in the history of language or its theory.

English became necessary for them to meet their vital needs. " Several methods are currently offered to students studying English .

One of them is the fundamental method. It requires at least 2-3 years of reading, in-depth study of grammar. This method is mainly useful in the training of professional translators, and at the end of the study students get a 48 % view of the world through the eyes of the "native speaker", the owner of the language(carrier) . Based on it, language is studied as a real and complete means of communication . Nowadays, the fundamental method has not changed its purpose , but many other methods have entered the field of competition with the fundamental method . One of them is the lingvosociocultural method. This method requires learning the language in a social and cultural environment. Proponents of it condemn the fact that students set themselves the goal of learning "dead" lexical-grammatical forms . According to them, "a person is a product of culture . So is the language. " In most cases , not learning the language in accordance with social life leads to many mistakes.

For example, a student learning English may use the phrase The Queen and Her relatives, which For those who don't know the language well Don't you want to go? and Would you like to go? the difference between the phrases is not great, but for the British they are different. In most cases, conferences ask, What other issues are you interested in?" "What problems are you interested in?" they translate. However, it should be noted that the word "problems" in English has a negative character, such as "What issues are you interesting?" which translates as preferred.

According to linguists, 52% of such errors are due to the direct translation of native language phrases into English, while 44% are determined by insufficient language learner capacity. The most important thing in the process of learning a language is how accurate the content of the information being transmitted is. Another method of teaching a new language is the communicative method, which is effectively used today in Europe and the United States.

Methods to acquire the knowledge of the second language As the name suggests , this method is based on interaction, in which it is important to read, write, speak, and understand the dialogues that form the basis of any language learning training . Of course, in this method, teachers pay more attention to the last two methods (speaking and comprehension of dialogues), and in such lessons you will not encounter complex word devices and serious vocabulary. The disadvantage of this method is that a student with vocabulary in any field can easily understand the content of the text in this context, but finds it difficult to communicate seriously with a specialist in the field . The purpose of this method is, first of all, to overcome the fear of communication. In today's fast-paced world , another method of teaching English that is more popular is the intensive method. It is based on about 25 percent of clichés, ie memorizing the most important phrases for communication .

Byron may not actually read the works, but he can communicate with his interlocutor when needed . The teacher who teaches using this method mainly uses dialogues as a weapon. Even through the intensive method , it is not possible to learn English in 2 weeks, but hard-working, selfemployed students can easily master the language in 3 months .By the end of the twentieth century, pedagogy had incorporated many interesting and effective methods and approaches. As a result of the enrichment of foreign language teaching methodology by scholars, it has become a complex and multidisciplinary field. Communicative approach. The development of modern techniques and technologies has pushed aside the usual methods of teaching, such as teaching through books , constant grammar exercises, reading and

translating The communicative approach eventually led to the formation of a communicative method based on the whole process The traditional grammatical-translation method does not shape language skills . Although a language learner has the skills to read and translate various texts of high complexity , he or she cannot apply his or her knowledge of a foreign language in real - life situations.

The communicative method allows the application of grammatical knowledge in the form of speaking and4. ConclusionSo, in order to learn the language in depth, to communicate easily, it is necessary to teach English effectively using the three methods listed above . In our opinion, first the student should be taught to speak English and in the second stage to be taught to think in that language. This is a rather difficult but feasible process. To do this, the English teacher should enrich the teaching method with a variety of games, communication with peers, errorfinding exercises, comparative analysis of texts, in addition to the standard approach .One of the important tasks is to increase the vocabulary.However, newly learned words should be stored not only in the passive form but also in the active form . In other words, the student must not only know the translation of the new word , but also be able to use it in his speech as well as in the texts he is writing . Modern development is characterized by the careful selection of foreign language teaching methods . At present, the most effective methods, various weapons and techniques are used in the training of specialists in various fields .

Scholars emphasize that the most important goal is to form a secondary language personality. Students need to master a new language at a fundamentally new level. In carrying out this task , it is important to separate it from the mother tongue in order to avoid misunderstandings .

The following criteria must be taken into account when choosing innovative methods :- to create a comfortable and free environment for the student, to strengthen the natural interest and passion in learning a new language ;- consideration of emotions, feelings, experiences in the educational process to strengthen oral, written and creative skills ;- to teach to speak the language independently, depending on the level of physical and emotional capabilities .Practical experience allows us to understand that the personality and interests of the student have a direct impact on the quality of learning a foreign language .

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